

The European Nanotechnology Community Informatics Platform: Bridging data and disciplinary gaps for industry and regulators

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Summary

This report describes the community-building and dissemination activities organized and performed by the NanoCommons consortium. In contrast to the original plans in the Description of Action (DoA) and suggested by the title of the document, the activities were not executed as standalone events but integrated into major events of the EU NanoSafety Cluster and other events of the nano community to be able to attract a large and diverse audience respecting the limited availability of the NanoCommons stakeholders. The main event co-organised by NanoCommons was the EU NanoSafety Cluster Week in Copenhagen, 7 - 10 Oct 2019, with multiple sessions and oral and poster presentations on different aspects of the NanoCommons infrastructure and special focus on the Transnational Access (TA). This was complemented by participating in a series of other nanosafety events specifically targeting exploitation towards stakeholder groups, such as the Nanotechnology Industry Association (NIA)'s 8th Annual Symposium, Brussels, 27 March 2019, EuroNanoForum 2019, Bucharest, 12 – 14 June 2019, 'Science is Wonderful!' exhibition, Brussels, 25 - 26 Sep 2019, the European Pilot-lines Project Network (EPPN) Workshop, San Sebastian, 5 Nov 2019, and the Boosting Innovation for EU Industry 2019 Conference, Brno, 19 Nov 2019. At all these events results from the active TA projects were presented, future TA calls were advertised and the TA application procedure, coordination and execution were demonstrated. Specifically, the NanoSafety Cluster Week offered the opportunity for researchers to directly discuss potential TA applications with the providers during the poster session. Finally, the SETAC Young Environmental Scientists (YES) meeting in Ghent, 5-10 February and the the 1st International Young Scientist Forum (IYSF), Salzburg, 9 - 10 Sep 2019 focused on how the TA can specifically support early-stage researchers.

List of Abbreviations

BfR - The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (NanoCommons partner)
BNN – BioNanoNet (NanoCommons partner)
CE-MS - Capillary electrophoresis - mass spectrometry
DoA - Description of Action
EPPN - European Pilot-lines Project Network
ENM - Engineered Nanomaterials
EwC – Edelweiss Connect GmbH (NanoCommons partner)
FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (data)
JRA - Joint Research Activities
KB - Knowledge Base
ICEENN - International Conference on Environmental Effects of Nanoparticles and Nanomaterial
IYSF- International Young Scientist Forum
LEITAT - Leitat Technological Center (NanoCommons partner)
NA - Networking Activities
NIA - Nanotechnology Industry Association
NSC - NanoSafety Cluster
NTUA - National Technical University of Athens (NanoCommons partner)
OITB - Open Innovation Test beds
PBPK - Physiologically based Pharmacokinetic (modelling)
PLUS - Paris Lodron University of Salzburg (NanoCommons partner)
PMML - Predictive Model Markup Language
QMRF - QSAR Model Report Format
QPRF - QSAR Prediction Reporting Format
QSAR - Quantitative Structure-Activity relationship
RA - Risk Assessment
SETAC - Society for Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
SME - small to medium enterprises
TA - Transnational Access
UoB - University of Birmingham (NanoCommons coordinator)
UKRI - United Kingdom Research & Innovation (NanoCommons partner)
YES - Young Environmental Scientists
WG - Working group (of the NSC)

Introduction

NanoCommons works internationally towards enhancing community activities (e.g. NanoSafety Cluster) by initiating and supporting different events in the scientific areas covered by the project and strengthening the nano-knowledge community (**Figure 1 and 2** and **Annex 1**).

In 2019 NanoCommons participated actively in different Conferences and Exhibition events as described below (see **Table 1**). One major event, EU NanoSafety Cluster Week: Building confidence in risk assessment and governance of nanomaterials innovation, was co-organised by NanoCommons. Similarly, NanoCommons members were involved in different dissemination and exploitation events dedicated to its stakeholders, i.e. scientists from academia, representatives from industry or regulation, international organisations, as well as the general public. Therefore, NanoCommons acted as a vehicle to progress the community efforts by bringing together the expertise and knowledge from stakeholders, research projects and organisations and disseminating outside the nano community.

Figure 1. Events organised (x2), co-organised (x6) or attended (x15) by NanoCommons partners

Figure 2. Geographical coverage of the events organised or attended by NanoCommons partners (the map does not include online events such as webinars).

Table 1. Major events attended in 2019

Event + web	Dates	Location	Type of audience
<u>SETAC Young Environmental Scientist (YES)</u>	5-10 Feb 2019	Ghent, BE	Young investigators (students, PhD candidates and early stage post docs)
<u>NIA's 8th Annual Symposium</u>	27 Mar 2019	Brussels, BE	Industry
<u>EuroNanoForum 2019</u>	12 – 14 Jun 2019	Bucharest, RO	Researchers, Regulators, Policy makers, Students, Risk assessors and Industry
<u>International Conference on Environmental Effects of Nanoparticles and Nanomaterials (ICEENN)</u>	1 – 4 Sep 2019	Vienna, AT	Mixed audience (scientists, regulatory, industry, developers, etc.)
<u>1st International Young Scientist Forum (IYSF)</u>	9 – 10 Sep 2019	Salzburg, AT	Young investigators (students, PhD candidates and early stage post docs)
<u>12th International Particle Toxicology Conference (IPTC)</u>	11 – 13 Sep 2019	Salzburg, AT	Mixed audience (scientists, regulatory, industry, developers, etc.)
<u>'Science is Wonderful!' exhibition</u>	25 – 26 Sep 2019	Brussels, BE	General public and Students
<u>NanoSafety Cluster Week</u>	7 – 10 Oct 2019	Copenhagen, DK	Mixed audience (scientists, regulatory, industry, developers, etc.)
<u>EPPN Workshop</u>	5 Nov 2019	San Sebastian, ES	Mixed audience (scientists, regulatory, industry, developers, etc.)
<u>Boosting Innovation for EU Industry 2019 Conference</u>	19 Nov 2019	Brno, CZ	Mixed audience (scientists, regulatory, industry, developers, etc.)

Events catalogue

A dedicated catalogue of Events¹ was implemented, including a list and description of conferences, workshops, hackathons, training sessions or webinars organised or attended by NanoCommons members. The description of the events also provides direct links to the relevant dissemination material from the NanoCommons Library (e.g., presentations, recordings, etc.) and generated for, or at, these events (see an example in **Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Example of an event description and documentation of the materials generated for that particular event.

¹ <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/events/>

Selected conferences and other exploitation events

SETAC YES meeting

5-10 February 2019 / Ghent, BE

The European branch of the [Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry](#) (SETAC) was established in 1990 as a forum for addressing environmental science challenges in a tripartite manner bringing together academia, regulators and industry. Almost 25% of all SETAC members are students and to ensure that the student voice was sufficiently represented in all SETAC activities, the Student Advisory Council (SAC) of SETAC was established in 2006. The main aim of the SAC Europe is to improve the communication among students within SETAC and to offer opportunities to students to get in contact with senior members of the society. One of the most important and well recognised projects of the SAC is the **Young Environmental Scientists (YES)** meeting which is organised annually by students for students (and recent graduates) with the main goal of bringing young researchers together and helping them develop their skills and network in an international setting. The 8th YES meeting was held in Ghent in February 2019, and as part of the conference had a 1-day workshop addressing the theme “**From test results to decision making – Driving environmental policy from the heart of Europe**”². As part of this workshop, Iseult Lynch presented a session on how to design environmental science experiments and capture the protocols and data in the most efficient and intelligent way (i.e. through electronic notebooks) in a format suitable for long-term storage and (open) sharing, using the NanoCommons approach. The workshop was attended by more than 120 students and recent graduates from 29 different countries.

NIA's 8th Annual Symposium

27 Mar 2019 / Brussels, BE

NIA welcomed members and guests to its 8th Annual Symposium in Brussels on March 27th 2019³. The event addressed key aspects of successful commercial delivery of nanotechnologies, including societal position, novel applications, challenges through the business pipeline, plus policy and regulator future vision (see Figure 4). The day included a focus session on nano in waste, with an in-depth analysis of the latest research, current business practice and future directions from a regulatory perspective. Speakers were representing the European Commission, ECHA, industry and research centres, with the event also featuring the 'Project Corner', with 18 H2020 projects linked to nanosafety research and innovation.

NanCommons was represented at the meeting by Tassos Papadiamantis (UoB), Lee Walker (UKRI), and Andreas Falk (BNN). The project was presented to the delegates through a poster featuring NanoCommons main purpose and procedures, together with additional materials such as TA application leaflets. Awareness of the project was specifically promoted within the industries stakeholder group and one-to-one dialogues with potential TA applicants were induced.

² <https://yes2019.setac.org/programme/workshop-day/>

³ <http://www.nanotechia.org/nias-8th-annual-symposium>

Figure 4. Dr David Carlander, Director of Regulatory Affairs, discussing recent developments in REACH registration for nanomaterials at the 8th Nanotechnology Industries Association Symposium, 27th March 2020.

EuroNanoForum 2019

12 – 14 Jun 2019 / Bucharest, RO

EuroNanoForum 2019 (“Nanotechnology and Advanced Materials Progress Under Horizon2020 and Beyond”⁴) was organised in Bucharest from 12-14 June under the patronage of the Romanian Presidency of the Council of the European Union. The represents one of the most significant European forums bringing together scientists, industry and policy makers:

- Europe’s largest networking conference focusing on nanotechnologies and advanced materials science, innovation and business;
- Open to the scientific community, representatives from industry, research and innovation, as well as policy makers;
- Offers excellent opportunities to debate cutting edge research and successful industrial implementations in the field

The event was attended by participants from Europe and across the globe and offered opportunities for discussions on cross-sectorial challenges focusing on both the industrial application of research results and future strategic research priorities in the area of Nanotechnology and Advanced Materials of the Horizon 2020 NMBP Programme and beyond.

⁴ <https://www.euronanoforum2019.eu/>

Figure 5. Images from the participation of NanoCommons at EuroNanoForum 2019 - Left: NanoCommons coordinator participating in the panel discussion and right the NanoCommons poster in the NSC booth.

NanoCommons had a strong presence at EuroNanoForum and was part of the Nanotechnology Industries Association NIA and EU NanoSafety Cluster Delegation (18 projects), more than 30 participants and a large **exhibition booth** promoting nanosafety and nanotechnology research in Europe and beyond (see Figure 5).

NanoCommons was specifically featured through a keynote **talk** by Prof Iseult Lynch and 4 **posters** presented by Dr Anastasios Papadiamantis (University of Birmingham), Dr Nathan Bossa (LEITAT), Dr Lucian Farcal (Edelweiss Connect) and Dr Martin Himly (Paris Lodron University Salzburg) and was also part of the NanoSafety Cluster **Workshop**, which focused on risk assessment in nanosafety and lessons learned from past research and directions for the future of the field.

International Conference on Environmental Effects of Nanoparticles and Nanomaterials (ICEENN)

1 – 4 Sep 2019 / Vienna, AT

NanoCommons was represented with a strong delegation of 10 attendees^[WLA1] at the 14th International Conference on Environmental Effects of Nanoparticles and Nanomaterials (ICEENN) taking place from the 1st to 4th September 2019 in Vienna, Austria⁵. ICEENN is the leading international conference in the field of environmental nanosciences covering main areas in environmental nanomaterial research such as ecotoxicology, nano-bio interactions, analytical methods, release, behaviour and fate of nanomaterials. Additionally, to the mentioned topics this most recent meeting dedicated a whole session to modelling, data repositories and nano-informatics which was co-chaired by one of our collaborative partners in the US from CEINT/Duke University (Mark Wiesner) and opened by a keynote lecture by Christine Hendren.

ICEENN was run back to back with the final conference of the NanoFASE project which produced additional opportunities to engage with scientist face to face to work on specific elements of complex data implementation into the NanoCommons data repositories as specifically selected NanoFASE data sets are case studies for the developed data platform. Iseult Lynch (UoB) presented “Towards FAIR data – NanoCommons & future infrastructure” that introduced benefits of FAIR data principles, the

⁵ <https://nano2019.univie.ac.at/iceenn/>

NanoCommons project and the TA services offered (see Figure 6). Next to that NanoCommons used this excellent opportunity to engage with a broad variety of stakeholders from regulatory authorities (e.g. ECHA) and industry as well as academia to advertise the NanoCommons platform. Specifically, at this stage in the project Transnational Access to the facilities of the partner institutions (e.g. modelling, ecotoxicology laboratories, nano-informatics etc.) is very attractive to scientists and NanoCommons generates great interest and attention for the TA calls at scientific conferences resulting in very satisfactory application numbers and extended networks.

Figure 6. Examples of slides from the presentation made by Iseult Lynch giving an overview of the NanoCommons project and an example of Transnational Access in SCINOTE online laboratory books.

12th International Particle Toxicology Conference (IPTC)

11 – 13 Sep 2019 / Salzburg, AT

NanoCommons partner PLUS, UoB and BfR were actively involved in the Scientific organising Committee of the **12th International Particle Toxicology Conference**, September 11-12, 2019, Salzburg, Austria, and as well in the **1st International Young Scientist Forum (IYSF)**, a satellite meeting, which was held September 9 and 10, 2019.

The latter was an open event specifically dedicated to young scientists (i.e. students, PhD candidates and early stage post docs) working in all fields in the broader area of particle and fibre toxicology. Approximately 50 young scientists participated in the IYSF interacting with each other and the experts. Participants did not only **discuss state-of-the-art science** to broaden their scientific knowledge but also allowed the young researchers to benefit from several specifically designed **interactive sessions** to advance their own career and research. In particular, the forum aimed to foster the spirit of teamwork among the participants, providing the opportunity to network globally and to establish own professional networks. Each participant **received a certificate of attendance** highlighting the contents of the forum. Furthermore, all young scientists had the opportunity to win one of the **several prestigious awards (Best Poster Award / Best Talk Award / Best Team Award)**.

Iseult Lynch (UoB) gave a very inspiring talk on the transformation of ENMs' properties through their whole life cycle and on how to approach risk assessment, thus, highlighting the necessity of monitoring these transformations by a thorough physico-chemical characterization coupled with a

detailed and specific data recording and management. Andrea Haase (BfR) and Martin Himly (PLUS) prompted the young scientists during the interactive sessions to work on the most challenging aspects of the field and to design research proposals to combat them. Notably, many of the young scientists did recognize the **need for a more extensive support by nano-informatics tools** (in particular when dealing with big data or systems biology approaches), as offered by NanoCommons. The brain storming results of the next generation of researchers are depicted in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7. Outcomes of the interactive sessions during the 1st International Young Scientists Forum

In a short oral presentation Dimitra Varsou (NTUA) introduced **“Read-across automated grouping and hazard endpoint predictions of nanoparticles based on mathematical optimization”** to the young scientists, thus, highlighting new nano-informatics approaches developed by the NTUA group relevant to NanoCommons deliverables.

During the IPTC⁶, which was attended by approx. 300 researchers, among them many leaders in the field, NanoCommons had a desk offering information material on the project and presenting its project video clip (Figure 8). Access to online training material was provided during the poster sessions and the TA services of the project were introduced to the researchers.

Figure 8. Photos capturing the scientific audience and the NanoCommons training booth within the poster session area at the 12th International Particle Toxicology Conference

⁶ <http://iptc2019.eu/programme.html>

‘Science is Wonderful!’ exhibition

25 – 26 Sep 2019 / Brussels, BE

NanoCommons was one of the two research infrastructure projects selected to participate in the European Commission’s 1st “Science is Wonderful” exhibition as part of the **Research and Innovation Days** on 24-26 September 2019 in Brussels⁷. The event gathered Europe’s best researchers, scientists, innovators and policy makers, as well as promoting engagement with science and research via the “Science is Wonderful” exhibition. The specific goal of the exhibition was to mobilise EU citizens and increase general awareness and understanding of how important research and innovation are in addressing societal challenges. The exhibition was attended by 5000+ school children aged 5 - 15.

NanoCommons was represented at the “Science is Wonderful” exhibition by Tassos Papadiamantis and Cristiana Gheorghe from UoB and Georgia Melagraki and Antreas Afantitis from NovaMechanics Ltd. (NanoCommons partner), as shown in Figure 9.

The NanoCommons stand and activities showcased our efforts around “Using nanotechnology safely in everyday life” and included hands-on activities such as using our machine learning tools to calculate a range of new properties related to nanomaterials that could predict if a specific nanomaterial will be safe for use in consumer products or not. The introduction video⁸ of NanoCommons project was also shown during this event.

Figure 9. Photos from NanoCommons’ participation at the ‘Science is Wonderful’ Exhibition in Brussels, 24-26 September 2019.

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/events/upcoming-events/european-research-and-innovation-days_en

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4yxW9P63JtE>

NanoSafety Cluster Week

7 – 10 Oct 2019 / Copenhagen, DK

NanoCommons, being co-organizer of the event, was also strongly represented by a series of talks across all sessions of the NanoSafety Cluster (NSC) Conference: Towards *in silico* nanosafety assessment – integrating experimental and computational approaches⁹ which took place on 8 - 9 Oct 2019. Additionally, NanoCommons partners participated in discussions during the NanoSafety Cluster (NSC) Steering Committee meeting (evening of 9th October) and the NSC Open Meeting (10 Oct 2019) as members of various working groups (e.g. WG-F on Data management, WG-D on Models and Tools for Risk Assessment, and WG-A on Communication, Training and Education), as well as co-hosting a hands-on training session on the ACEnano protocols database which is being integrated into NanoCommons to support its wider uptake and implementation.

Below, a short summary of each NanoCommons talk, the TA and overview posters:

Keynote Session 1 – Introduction to the organising and sponsoring projects (Iseult Lynch, UoB)

Prof. Iseult Lynch opened the conference, thanked the local organising committee and the CaLIBRATE team for the support with arrangements, and the coordinators of the NanoSolveIT and NanoInformatIX projects who had co-organised the scientific programme along with NanoCommons.

Prof. Lynch presented a short overview of the NanoCommons project, highlighting its unique approach as a research infrastructure, with three pillars of activity - joint research activities (JRA) to develop the infrastructure itself and the services that it can offer, the networking activities (NA), such as this conference, aiming to integrate best practice from across the community and embedding NanoCommons approaches in the community practice, and the TA activities providing funded access to the tools and services to support researchers in making their nanosafety data open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable), in line with the EU's policies on open data. The presentation highlighted some of the advantages and opportunities of open data, and touched upon the tools and services currently available and under development, indicating that there were opportunities to learn more via the TA posters during the poster session, from the upcoming keynote presentation on the NanoCommons Knowledge Base (KB) from Thomas Exner, for example. The short introduction finished with a call to action for the community to get involved since NanoCommons is the community research infrastructure so it is driven by community needs and requirements.

***In silico* characterization of nanomaterials for predictive toxicology (Vladimir Lobaskin, University College Dublin)**

Dr Vladimir Lobaskin presented how *in silico* characterization is currently used to complement lab characterization of nanomaterials and fill the information gaps where necessary or deliver specific advanced properties of materials such as hydration or interaction with biomolecules. The first principle methodologies are currently developed in EU H2020 SmartNanoTox and NanoSolveIT projects and implemented as data analysis and modelling tools in the NanoCommons KB. The presentation specifically highlighted that the information provided by material modelling is essential for the development of nanoinformatics.

⁹ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/eu-nanosafety-cluster-week-2019-7-10-october-2019-copenhagen-denmark/>

Jaqpot - An open-source web platform for creating, using, testing and sharing predictive models in nano-informatics within the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase (Philip Doganis, National Technical University Of Athens)

Dr Philip Doganis presented how the nanosafety community needs for easy use, propagation and evaluation of NM-specific QSAR and biokinetics computational models can be satisfied by Jaqpot¹⁰. Jaqpot is a computational platform developed by NTUA for *in silico* modelling of chemical compounds for users to systematically produce, collect, organize, validate, store and share predictive models relevant to nanosafety. Its functionalities and the models hosted in Jaqpot are being extended through its integration into the modelling infrastructure developed by NanoCommons. The presentation underlined the platform's capabilities, being a cloud-ready web platform operating over both a User Interface and an Application Programming Interface that incorporates algorithms from various established open-source machine learning and data analysis toolkits in Java, R and Python. Through specially designed libraries, users can turn their nanoQSAR and PBPK models into model web services accompanied by various sets of tools for QMRF and QPRF report generation, PMML representation, ontological annotation and visualization of modelling data and results. Finally, Dr Doganis especially highlighted the provision of both machine- and human-friendly access, the variety of open source data analysis toolkits and the ability to produce models with the necessary information for risk assessment as key features for Jaqpot to serve community needs in nanosafety modelling effectively.

Exploring the complete corona of nanomaterials – the interplay between the small molecule and proteins coronas (Andrew Chetwynd, University of Birmingham)

Dr Andrew Chetwynd presented the work carried out by SCIEX on the application of capillary electrophoresis - mass spectrometry (CE-MS) on the characterisation of the complete biomolecular corona of nanomaterials. Initial work published in *Nanomaterials* in 2019 was presented where a sample preparation technique was developed to recover as much of the protein corona as possible prior to CE-MS analysis. Subsequently new data on the metabolite corona was presented. 6 nanomaterials were exposed to both cationic and anionic mixtures of polar metabolites and the concentration of metabolites adsorbed to the NMs quantified by CE-MS. Finally the role of proteins in the recruitment of the metabolite corona was discussed as a promising future area of research to fully understand the formation of the complete corona.

Dissolution behaviour of a library of 37 nanomaterials in simplified physiological media (Anastasios Papadiamantis, University of Birmingham)

Dr Anastasios Papadiamantis gave a talk on the potential for grouping ENMs based on their dissolution behaviour. The study covered a library of 37 different ENMs used during the FP7 project NanoMILE, which were exposed in two simplified physiological media: the neutral lung environment (pH: 7.0) and the low-pH gastric environment (pH: 1.5). The ENM were fully characterised with respect to their physicochemical properties (chemical composition, morphology, coating, coating charge, size, polydispersity index, hydrodynamic diameter, ζ -potential, specific) or computed using respective

¹⁰ <https://app.jaqpot.org>

measurements (energy band gap, geometric surface area) and further enriched with molecular descriptors like core metal electronegativity, valency and atomic/ionic radii. Details on the non-linear statistical analysis used were provided and the conclusions included insights on the parameters that contributed the most to the data variance, were mostly correlated and could be used to explain ENM dissolution behaviour.

Towards the development of a community-based state-of-the-art Risk Assessment toolbox within the NanoCommons Knowledge base (Dr Philip Doganis, National Technical University Of Athens)

This talk focused on the current state of the art of the work towards developing a comprehensive risk assessment (RA) toolbox by collecting, interlinking and integrating tools and methodologies for the different components of the RA process, namely exposure modeling, hazard prediction and eventually RA itself. Subsequently, Dr Philip Doganis presented the efforts for full integration of the RA tools with high quality curated datasets arising from FP7 and H2020 nanosafety projects that are being integrated to populate the NanoCommons Knowledge base. Focus was put on how NanoCommons partners are formulating checklists/guidelines and best practices for the efficient use of these tools independently or as components of complete RA workflows. The RA toolbox will be integrated in the project's knowledge infrastructure and serve the calculation of initial exposure estimates, hazard reference points and the respective Risk Characterization Ratios allowing for the assessment of the effect of a range of mitigation strategies/measures that are available or can be applied, tailored to specific NMs and their application-specific consideration.

Plenary 4: The NanoCommons knowledge infrastructure built to support the research communities, industrial users and regulators in the area of nanomaterials safety assessment (Thomas Exner, Edelweiss Connect GmbH)

The talk presented how NanoCommons reduces the fragmentation of nanosafety related data and knowledge by aligning and semantically linking available resources from major European and international nanosafety projects and infrastructures, providing new harmonized resources when needed and ensuring access following the FAIR principles (**F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable) whenever possible in an open and free of charge manner. Then, the outputs to be shared via the NanoCommons knowledge infrastructure, were presented: i) Central data access to stored data or linked data sources via a variety of tools (e.g. web interfaces, application programming interfaces), ii) Metadata-rich datasets from experiments and modelling/simulations, iii) Protocols and Standard Operating Procedures, iv) Quality Assurance, v) Concepts, guidance and templates for data curation, vi) Automated annotation pipelines, and vii) Data standards. Finally, it was described how this integrated design offers easy and harmonized access to a variety of datasets (physicochemical, hazard, exposure, fate) as well as data management, data mining and data visualisation tools for researchers from academia and industry, as well as regulators, ensuring their optimal use and joint further development (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Thomas Exner (EwC) presenting the data warehouse of NanoCommons

Interactive Poster session:

During the interactive poster sessions a number of posters for the NanoCommons TA services and the e-infrastructure of resources with online training materials, their content, what to expect from them and where to find them, was provided. Martin Himly (PLUS) presented the NanoCommons e-infrastructure in a short teaser presentation with more details during the poster session (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Martin Himly (PLUS) presenting the e-infrastructure of NanoCommons

Links to the posters and their abstracts:

- Martin Himly, Mark Geppert, Anastasios Papadiamantis, Albert Duschl, Iseult Lynch, and the NanoCommons consortium. Online training tools for nanosafety assessment – NanoCommons for researchers and safety assessors in industry, academia and regulatory authorities. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3693721.

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- Beatriz Alfaro Serrano, Susanne Resch, Anastasios Papadiamantis, Iseult Lynch, and Andreas Falk. Transnational Access @ NanoCommons. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3693694.
 - Georgia Melagraki, Antreas Afantitis, and Iseult Lynch. Enalos Cloud Platform Transnational Access Services Through NanoCommons H2020 Infrastructure Project. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3695647.
 - Perikilis Tsiros, Dingsheng Li, Pantelis Karatzas, Philip Doganis, and Haralambos Sarimveis. PBPK modelling on the Jaqpot web platform - a PAA-peg nanoparticles case study. DOI: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3691860.
 - Lee A. Walker, Marianne Matzke, Stephen Lofts, and Claus Svendsen. NanoCommons - Opportunities for accessing nanoinformatics and predictive models for environmental fate. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3700691
 - Anastasios G. Papadiamantis and Iseult Lynch. H2020 NanoCommons Transnational Access Services: Data management in nanosafety research. From bench to database thus streamlining analysis and publication. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3700710

NanoCommons TA - UoB: Data management in nanosafety research. From bench to database thus streamlining analysis and publication

This UoB Transnational Access service is focussed on services related to dataset management and accessibility - including the use of electronic laboratory notebooks, the annotation of existing datasets with ontology terms to facilitate the dataset integration into the NanoCommons database, support in the analysis of datasets from a statistical viewpoint, and support in making data FAIR. Our data management services span the entire data lifecycle - from experimental design through to data generation, analysis and storage, linking experimental protocols and bibliographic metadata, and long-term deposition of datasets. Services can be accessed individually or as a package, tailored to individual needs. Services are applicable to individual datasets or to entire portfolios of data arising from research projects or teams.

Protocol and data warehouse training co-organized by ACEnano and NanoCommons:

The aim was to introduce the unique approach of the ACEnano Knowledge Protocols and Data warehouse designed to disseminate protocols and their variations and to store, manage and share data for physico-chemical characterisation of nanomaterials under standard conditions as well as at different life stages. To improve reproducibility as well as to identify small variations in the used protocols, the ACEnano protocol system uses highly structured questionnaires to document all experimental steps and specific settings in an annotated and computer-readable way, which are then linked to the corresponding data as metadata. The training first introduced how to add protocols, create data workflows and upload data following this concept. The second aim was to introduce the concepts of protocols and data annotations and the use of ontologies in the context of ACEnano. The latter is optimised to allow the integration of the ACEnano data into the NanoCommons knowledge infrastructure based on the semantic mapping of metadata. Besides making the ACEnano data available to NanoCommons users, ACEnano also functions as showcase and prototype for integration of external data warehouses performed as current and future TA activities.

EPPN Workshop

5 Nov 2019 / San Sebastian, ES

The European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs (EPPN)¹¹ organised a workshop on Pilot production lines for the health, transport, and industry¹² (*content open to EPPN members only*) in San Sebastian (Spain) on November 5th, 2019. This EPPN Workshop, addressed the opportunity to exchange experiences between pilot plants and establish future relationships with the industry. The agenda is provided in Annex II.

Achieving successful pilot production, from a laboratory scale to small pilot plants, is a major success factor in the innovation and management potential of ENM producing companies. The attendees of the workshop were able to learn about the opportunities that these open access pilot plants offer to European industry; furthermore, they had the opportunity to visit some of them on-site and get to know first-hand their characteristics.

Figure 12. Organisers and participants of the EPPN workshop 2019 (@EPPN workshop Committee).

The workshop was attended by about 100 participants from academia, industry, investors, scientific community, policy makers and end-users, many of which were small to medium enterprises (SME). Beatriz Alfaro, from BioNanoNet (BNN), presented the NanoCommons project, **supporting the pilots and the Open Innovation Test beds** (OITB) as NanoCommons provides access to state-of-the-art of NanoCommons expertise (in **nanoinformatics and data management tools, modelling and risk assessment services**) free of charge (by means of the TA¹³ activities) and taking advantage of the NanoCommons services, facilities and knowledge to advance their work, solve problems and take their research to the next level (Figure 12).

¹¹ <https://www.eppnetwork.com/>

¹² <https://eppnetwork.com/post/8072> → Content open to EPPN members only

¹³ <https://www.nanocommons.eu/ta-access/>

Boosting Innovation for EU Industry 2019 Conference

19 Nov 2019 / Brno, CZ

Lee Walker (UKRI) presented the work of the project as an invited speaker at the Boosting Innovation Tour Conference held at BVV Trade Fairs, Brno, Czech Republic. The conference showcased several successful examples of innovation support with special emphasis on the Czech Republic, and was an opportunity to provide feedback to high level EU representatives and discuss the needs of the local industry. The event was attended by over 100 delegates including representatives from research academic organisations, industrials (including many SMEs), and regional, national and international trade and research bodies.

The main objective of the conference was to present different EU national and regional initiatives to support innovation, access to research and technology infrastructure and financial support to boost innovation beyond 2020. As part of this programme Lee Walker gave a short presentation highlighting the aims and approaches in promoting improved nanoinformatics through the provision of transnational access initiative (Figure 13).

As part of the event there was a matchmaking initiative in which discussions were held with companies and research institutes to explore the potential for development of TA applications. A productive discussion was held with Michal Urbánek, Nano Group Leader at the Central European Institute of Technology (CEITEC) which led to further discussions around holding a joint event to promote awareness NanoCommons and encourage applications for TAs from users of the CEITEC facilities.

The CEITEC Nano Research Infrastructure provides complex equipment, expertise and methods for nanotechnology and advanced materials R&D. The CEITEC Nano facilities for nanofabrication, nanocharacterization, structural analysis and X-ray tomography enable complete fabrication of nanostructures and nanodevices and their characterization down to the sub-nanometre level in an entirely clean environment. In our discussions it was apparent that provision of support in nanoinformatics would benefit users of the CEITEC Nano core facility. The next steps are to schedule and plan for a joint NanoCommons/CEITEC event in 2020.

Lee Walker @LeewWalker · Nov 19, 2019
Happy to be an invited speaker at the EU Boosting Innovation Roadshow at Brno, Czech Republic. Jana Drbohlavova starting the meeting with a welcome to Brno

Figure 13. Social media posting from Lee Walker (UKRI) while attending Boosting Innovation for EU Industry 2019 Conference, 19th November 2019, Brno, Czech Republic.

Conclusions and future plans

NanoCommons members organised, co-organised and participated in 23 events during the second year of the project, which are described in detail in this report. The NanoCommons sessions, platform and poster presentations were arranged around and focused on community building and exploitation and presented the active Transnational Access (TA) projects, advertised the future TA calls and demonstrated the TA application procedure, coordination and execution. These dissemination activities reached diverse stakeholder groups due to the different target audiences of the events such as industry at NIA's 8th Annual Symposium and the Boosting Innovation for EU Industry 2019 Conference, at the EPPN Workshop, or a broader audience (linking academia, industry and regulators) the EuroNanoForum 2019 or the EU NanoSafety Cluster Week as well as the general public at the 'Science is Wonderful!' exhibition and early-stage researchers at the 1st International Young Scientist Forum (IYSF), respectively. All slides and posters of these events are available in the online NanoCommons library and are linked to relevant NanoCommons services and TA offerings. Based on the achievements described here, NanoCommons will continue its community outreach and dissemination activities in the upcoming years by organising and co-organising sessions and satellite events during major nanosafety conferences and workshops. A detailed plan can be found in Deliverable 2.6.

Annex

List of events organised, co-organised or joined by NanoCommons consortium

Categories	Name	Start date	End date	Location	Website
Hackathon	1st NanoCommons Hackathon on "Ontological Annotation of Datasets"	2018-10-09		Greece	https://www.nanocommons.eu/1st-nanocommons-hackathon-ontological-annotations-of-datasets/
Hackathon, Conference, Workshop	OpenTox Euro 2018	2018-10-09	2018-10-11	Greece	https://opentox.net/events/opentox-euro-2018
Hackathon, Workshop	OpenRiskNet/NanoCommons ontology meeting	2018-12-13	2018-12-14	Belgium	https://openrisknet.org/events/45/
Symposium	NIA's 8th Annual Symposium - 2019	2019-03-27		Belgium	http://www.nanotechia.org/activities/nias-8th-annual-symposium
Workshop	SusChem Workshop: "Towards a New SusChem SIRA"	2019-05-16	2019-05-17	Belgium	http://www.suschem.org/events/towards-a-new-suschem-sira-workshop
Training, Workshop	Piemonte Spring School	2019-05-22	2019-05-24	Italy	http://www3.ubu.es/nanogentools/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/SSPiamonte19.html
Trade show / Exhibition, Conference, Workshop	EuroNanoForum 2019	2019-06-12	2019-06-14	Romania	https://www.euronanoforum2019.eu/
Webinar, Training	Introduction of the Nanoparticle protein Corona Modelling Tool	2019-06-25		Online	https://www.nanocommons.eu
Project meeting	4th NanoCommons General Assembly Meeting	2019-07-01	2019-07-02	Cyprus	
Workshop	Joint NanoCommons – NanoSolveIT – RISKGONE Meeting	2019-07-04		Cyprus	
Conference, Workshop	ICEENN 2019 (International Conference on Environmental Effects of Nanoparticles and Nanomaterials)	2019-09-01	2019-09-04	Austria	https://nano2019.univie.ac.at/home/
Training, Conference	1st International Young Scientist Forum (IYSF)	2019-09-09	2019-09-10	Austria	http://iptc2019.eu/Satellite+meetings/IYSF+2019.htm

Categories	Name	Start date	End date	Location	Website
Trade show / Exhibition, Training, Conference	12th International Particle Toxicology Conference (IPTC)	2019-09-11	2019-09-13	Austria	http://iptc2019.eu/
Trade show / Exhibition	Science is Wonderful	2019-09-25	2019-09-26	Belgium	https://ec.europa.eu/research/mariecurieactions/events/science-wonder-ful_en
Training, Conference, Workshop	NanoSafety Cluster Week	2019-10-07	2019-10-10	Denmark	https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/eu-nanosafety-cluster-week-2019-7-10-october-2019-copenhagen-denmark/
Workshop	EU-U.S. NanoEHS Communities of Research (CORs) Workshop	2019-10-15	2019-10-16	France	https://us-eu.org/save-the-date-october-15-16-2019/
Training, Workshop	OpenRiskNet Final Workshop	2019-10-23	2019-10-24	Netherlands	https://openrisknet.org/events/74/
Webinar	Building Confidence for Risk Assessment and Governance of Nanomaterials: the caLIBRAte project	2019-10-29		Online	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/building-confidence-for-risk-assessment-and-governance-of-nanomaterials-tickets-71621203949
Conference, Workshop	OpenTox Euro 2019	2019-10-29	2019-10-31	Switzerland	https://opentox.net/events/opentox-euro-2019
Webinar	Nano-Risk Governance Portal: Introduction and Launch	2019-10-31		Online	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/nano-risk-governance-portal-introduction-and-launch-tickets-71624190883
Workshop	EPPN Workshop (European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs)	2019-11-05		Spain	https://www.eppnetwork.com/
Conference	Boosting Innovation for EU Industry	2019-11-19		Czechia	https://www.ideal-ist.eu/event/boosting-innovation-eu-industry
Webinar	Optimal descriptors: genesis, state of the art, future	2019-12-17		Online	

Agenda EPPN Workshop

Pilot production lines for the health, transport and industry-EPPN workshop

**Venue: Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Gipuzkoa, Paseo Mikeletegi 53
San Sebastian, SPAIN**

Date: November 5th 2019

Successful pilot production, from lab scale to small production, is an important success factor for the innovation potential and management of every manufacturing company.

EPPN: EPPN is the **European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs**. Pilot facilities respond rapidly to scaling-up needs, which are essential for SMEs and start-ups. They are tools to train next generation, upgrade European industry to stay competitive, generate business and potentially help create new business, jobs and growth across Europe by offering a dedicated infrastructure and service ecosystem.

This EPPN Workshop, in collaboration with SPRI, Business Development Agency of the Basque Government, dependent on the Department of Economic Development and Infrastructures and its Science, Technology and Innovation Network, address and gives the opportunity for exchange between pilot facilities and Open innovation test beds and for establishing further relations with industry.

Attendees will be able to know the opportunities that these open access pilot plants offer to European industry, especially SMEs and startups, as well as visit some of them on-site and learn first-hand their characteristics.

AGENDA

9:30-10.00 Registration

10:00-11:15 Welcome. EU, national and regional perspectives

- Welcome- Alberto Fernández, Basque Government
- Pilots and Innovation test-beds landscape, Maria Moragues-European Commission (Video conference)
- EIT Innovation Communities – A success to integrate the Knowledge Triangle- Antoni Pijoan - EIT Manufacturing
- Spanish participation in OITBs
Nieves Gonzalez, CDTI
- Basque Industry 4.0 -A regional example of an innovation hub
Rikardo Bueno, BRTA

11:15-11:45 **Coffee break**

11:45-13:00 Initiatives supporting pilots & OITBs

- EPPN – Opportunities for SMEs, & marketplace-Paula Galvao, INL
- ACEnano- Analytical innovation for complex nanomaterial characterisation- Andy Chetwynd, University of Birmingham
- NanoCommons - How it can help you?-Beatriz Alfaro, BioNanoNet

13:00-14:30: Networking Lunch + Transfer to Test Bed Facilities

14:30-17:30 SECTORIAL PARALLEL SESSIONS AND PILOTS VISITS

Parallel session 1: Pilot lines and OITBs for INDUSTRY AND TRANSPORT SECTORS	
Venue: TECNALIA. Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Gipuzkoa Pº Mikeletegi, 1-3	
14:30-14:50	IZADI-NANO2INDUSTRY: Nanotechnology reaches industry Maider García de Cortazar, TECNALIA
14:50-15:10	Intelligent Open Test Bed for Materials Tribological Characterisation Services Alberto Alberdi, TEKNIKER
15:10-15:30	Battery Manufacturing Pilot Line as a tool for technology transference to the energy storage Industry Oscar Miguel, CIDETEC Energy Storage
15:30-15:50	Pilot for the fabrication of nanostructures across large and non-planar surfaces Isabel Obieta, TECNALIA
15:50-16:10	FormPlanet – Sheet metal forming testing hub Eduard Piqueras-Eurecat
16:10	VISIT TO TECNALIA FACILITIES: buckypapers & composites manufacturing automatization
17:00	VISIT TO CIDETEC Surface Engineering facilities: <i>Anaphoretic electrocoating pilot line and other electrochemical surface treatment and complementary pilot lines</i>

Parallel session 2: Pilot Lines and OITBs for the HEALTH SECTOR	
Venue: CIDETEC. Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Gipuzkoa Pº Miramón, 196	
14:30-14:50	TB-MED An Open Innovation test bed for the development of high-risk medical devices Iraida Loinaz, CIDETEC Nanomedicine
14:50-15:10	Boosting the adoption of nano-enabled medical technologies: SAFE-N-MEDTECH Open Innovation Test Bed Ángel del Pozo, BOKERALTY Research Institute
15:10-15:30	MDOT – a platform for simplified conformity assessment of medical devices Ulrich Froriep, Fraunhofer Institute for Toxicology and Experimental Medicine
15:30-15:50	INNPAPER-Configurable and recyclable electronic platform based on paper Jamal Tallal, CEA
15:50-16:10	The third nervous system-Bioelectronics at the Printed Electronics Arena – a hub for prototyping Björn Norberg, RISE AB
16:10-17.15	VISIT TO CIDETEC Nanomedicine Facilities- <i>Pilot Plant for GMP Manufacturing of Investigational Medicinal Products</i>